

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

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ABSTRACT: The present study was focused on determining and analyzing the extent of home learning environment and parent-teacher ecology towards the academic performance and positive social behavior of Grade 6 pupils in the S.Y. 2022-2023. The target respondents of the study included Grade 6 students.

The study utilized the descriptive quantitative research design in gathering data and information for the completion of this research endeavor. The survey questionnaire was utilized as the main tool for the data gathering process of the research.

The researcher concluded that based on the students' experience in their home learning environment, this is more related to the way that they are being influenced by the kind of environment they have at home; that the established good relations between parent and teacher can be concluded to have a significant role in terms of helping children or learners learn better and integrate or incorporate important values and attitudes into their lives as part of their daily learning experience at school; and that academic success among the learners can be concluded to be attainable with the help of parents and teachers and the willingness of the pupils themselves.

On the other hand, the researcher recommended that conduct parent-teacher conferences and meetings help the parents develop better attitudes and approaches to guide their children in doing assignments or projects; that in order to enrich the parent-teacher ecology aspect, parent-teacher conferences are again recommended in order to effectively address any emergence of problems and misunderstandings between parents and teachers.

KEYWORDS: academic performance, behavior, home learning environment, parent-teacher ecology

INTRODUCTION

One of the many reasons why children are sent to school in an early age is connected with the intention of helping them to discover and continuously hone their knowledge and skills so that one day, they can be able to apply or use it for seeking their dream career or profession and be of greater use for the continued improvement of their respective families and communities. In fact, according to the study conducted by Tadese et al. (2022) it was noted that students must dedicate a significant amount of their time to their study in order to graduate with strong academic standing.

Academic performing students are more likely to have better employment benefits, higher incomes, higher levels of self-confidence and self-esteem, lower levels of anxiety and depression, and lower rates of substance addiction. It was understood that the concept of academic achievement or success is crucial for future advancement in technologically demanding professions. Further, academic achievement has a favorable impact on conduct and social connections with family, friends, and peers. Successful pupils acquire reading, writing, and critical-thinking abilities that will be useful in the future. It's crucial to remember that academic achievement is only one component of a person's total growth and wellbeing. Personal interests, beliefs, emotional intelligence, and practical skills are other elements that have a significant impact on future outcomes and success in a variety of occupations. Beyond typical academic achievements, various people may define success and find fulfillment in different ways.

Moreover, the degree to which a student, instructor, or institution has met their immediate or long-term educational objectives is referred to as academic achievement or academic performance. Academic achievement is the completion of educational milestones such secondary school diplomas and bachelor's degrees in the near future (Kayser, (2021); Alyahyan & Dustegor, 2020).

Also, academic accomplishment and academic performance are terms that can be used interchangeably to describe the outcomes of educational activities, tests, or evaluations. It demonstrates a student's academic performance in terms of information acquisition, the development of abilities, and compliance with predetermined criteria or expectations.

The most important aspect influencing a student's academic performance is their home environment. Several aspects of the home environment that are absent in our homes for our kids have a negative effect and have little bearing on students' academic progress. As such, academic achievement, as according to Jain and Mohta (2019), which refers to students' performance in academic

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

subjects. As a result, in a supportive setting, the student finds it simpler to learn new material and can give their studies their whole attention. A learner's interaction with their environment is what constitutes learning. As soon as a child is born, learning begins at home.

The child learns a lot from the family in every way. The home environment has a big impact on learning. Both a child's personality and academic performance are significantly influenced by their home environment. The home has a huge influence on a child's academic progress. How well a child performs in school is influenced by the knowledge they are exposed to at home and how their family supports their desire for study. Also, a number of studies have demonstrated a positive relationship between the family environment and academic achievement. Also, it was shown that the home environment has a significant influence on how well higher secondary students perform academically. Additionally, factors including the home environment, family expectations, parental involvement, intellectual stimulation, and parental encouragement have a significant impact on how well learners succeed academically. In addition, there is also the need to take in consideration on how schools or educational institutions tend to connect and communicate with parents affects the degree and type of parental involvement in their children's education at home.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study aimed to assess the extent of home learning environment and parent-teacher ecology towards the perceived academic performance and positive social behavior of Grade 6 pupils.

METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive quantitative research design in gathering data and information for the completion of this research endeavor. The said design will be utilized in this study since it involved collecting and interpreting data to gather information needed to serve its purpose.

The goal of this research design is to summarize comprehensively, in everyday terms, specific events experienced by individuals or groups of individuals. This design is also well regarded in formulating policies in the local, national, or international level (Calmorin, 2017).

In this context, the researcher focuses on to assess the perceived effect of home learning environment and parent-teacher ecology towards the academic performance and positive social behavior of Grade 6 pupils.

B. Respondents of the Study

These respondents of the study were the grade six students of Padre Garcia Central School, Padre Garcia District, Division of Batangas during school year 2022 -2023. The respondents came from four sections of Grade VI namely, VI-Sagittarius with 34 students, VI Taurus who also have 34 students, VI Pieces with 33 student and Grade VI Scorpio with 35 students with the total of 136 students. They were selected through total enumeration.

C. Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher prepared a letter of request addressed to the Division Superintendent of Batangas through the Public Schools District Supervisor, and the school heads of public elementary schools to seek permission to distribute the questionnaire to the grade six students. After the approval and endorsement, the researcher will administer the questionnaire to the respondents. The researcher conducted the Pilot Testing to thirty (30) Grade 5 students of Padre Garcia Central School. The researcher asked the help of a statistician in treating the obtained data from the questionnaire. After having a positive response from the statistician regarding the pilot testing, the researcher administered to the questionnaire to the intended respondents, the grade six students of Padre Garcia Central School with a total number of 136 students. Again, the researcher seeks the help of statistician in order to treat the obtained data from the questionnaire

D. Data Analysis

The data gathered were analyzed using the statistical treatment appropriate to the study. The results were interpreted to answer the questions and achieve the aim of the study. The data collected were treated confidentially and were used only for the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presented the analyzed and interpreted findings based on the specific problems and hypothesis that were formulated at the beginning of the study.

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

Table 1. Student-Respondent Experience on Home Learning Environment in Terms of Children’s Participation in Learning Activities

Children’s Participation in Learning Activities	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. I listen in our lessons we have in class	3.79	0.41	Highly Experienced
2. I pay attention to the lesson being discussed by the teacher and enjoy our activities in class	3.72	0.45	Highly Experienced
3. I join and participate our activities in class	3.60	0.49	Highly Experienced
4. I submit my journal/worksheet about the lesson on time	3.66	0.48	Highly Experienced
5. I always share in our recitation	3.45	0.50	Highly Experienced
Mean	3.65	0.26	Highly Experienced

Legend:	Range of Means	Verbal Interpretation
3.50 – 4.00	Highly Experienced	
2.50 – 3.49	Experienced	
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Experienced	
1.00 – 1.49	Never Experienced	

As shown in the findings presented in Table 1, with regards to the student-respondent experience home learning environment in terms of children’s participation in learning activities, it can be seen that the indicator 1 “I listen to our lessons in class” had the highest mean of 3.79 and verbally interpreted as Highly Experienced. The children’s participation can be considered to be mostly be associated with the way in which children or learners are performing and listening in class. The possible reason behind this is that listening during class lessons can allow the learners to better understand the lesson and through such improved understanding, this can allow them to have increased participation in various activities that they are having or will be having in class. It can also be interpreted that the easiest thing to do of the student nowadays is to listen to the lesson they have in class since listening is just hearing words and sound while understanding the context of the lesson we have in class. Also, actively listening in class can lead to improved academic performance. When students understand the material and actively engage with it, they are more likely to perform well on assignments, exams, and other assessments.

On the other hand, the indicator 5 “I always share in our recitation” had the lowest mean of 3.45. Even though it was recorded as the lowest mean, it is also o interpreted as Highly Experienced which mean that is still evident in class. Class recitation encourages active participation form all student. It aids timid or reserved pupils in gaining self-assurance in communicating their views and opinions. Recitation in classes may also be more interesting and useful for students with diverse learning styles than typical lectures. Specially when our topic was very familiar to the class and very timely with their generation, they tend to be so excited to raise their hand and share their own experience that the teacher notes to be beneficial to student and the teacher herself. When students share their understanding of a concept or summarize key points, it helps reinforce their own understanding. By explaining the information to their peers, they consolidate their knowledge and identify any gaps or misconceptions. Participating in class discussions and sharing information builds students' confidence in expressing their ideas in a public setting. It allows them to develop their voice, share their unique viewpoints, and become active contributors to the classroom community. To add, sharing in class promotes an interactive and inclusive learning environment, fostering deeper understanding, collaboration, and the development of important skills necessary for academic and personal growth.

The overall weighted mean for children’s participation in learning activities was 3.65 and was also verbally interpreted as Highly Experienced. This interprets that with regards to the children’s participation in learning activities, this is mostly being done or manifested in the way in which the students are being able to listen attentively in the lessons or discussions that they have in class, thus considering the way they are participating in learning activities, and this starts first in listening or engaging in class discussions. It can also infer that children’s participation in learning activities is a manifestation of good home learning environment. Also, when students actively listen, it demonstrates respect for the teacher and their expertise. This positive attitude can foster a stronger relationship with the teacher, leading to more meaningful interactions, personalized guidance, and potentially opening doors to further academic opportunities.

Further, as according to John-Akinola & Nic-Gabhainn (2014) class participation is an essential component of student learning it is during this aspect that students learn to communicate themselves in a way that others can understand when they speak out in class and they also learn how to collect information to improve their comprehension of a topic by asking questions. Furthermore, class participation and interaction are essential to learning in many subjects because it allows students to digest knowledge rather than merely receive it. A discussion's objective is to get students to practice thinking about the course material and this can be helpful for improving the learning experience of students.

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

Table 2. Student-Respondent Experience on Home Learning Environment in Terms of Parent-Child Interactions

Parent-Child Interaction	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. My parents always ask me about our class and assignments	3.53	0.54	Highly Experienced
2. My parents always attend school meetings to know my progress in school	3.42	0.53	Experienced
3. My parents identify my weaknesses in learning	3.55	0.50	Highly Experienced
4. My parents identify my interests and strengths as a learner	3.66	0.48	Highly Experienced
5. My parents always assist/guide me in my assignments or projects	3.40	0.57	Experienced
Mean	3.51	0.29	Highly Experienced

Legend:	Range of Means	Verbal Interpretation
3.50 – 4.00	Highly Experienced	
2.50 – 3.49	Experienced	
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Experienced	
1.00 – 1.49	Never Experienced	

As shown in the findings presented in Table 2, with regards to the student-respondent experience home learning environment in terms of parent-child interactions, it can be seen that the indicator 4 “My parents identify my interests and strengths as a learner” had the highest mean of 3.66 and interpreted as Highly Experienced. With regards to parent-child interaction, it is possible that the identification of interests and strengths of a learner was regarded as important as in this way and in gaining such information, this can help the parents to determine the ideal kind of support that they can give or provide to their child and decrease tendency of pressuring them to learn. Also, one of the possible reasons of this result is that parents give rewards whenever they got achievement in school thus resulting for the students to become open with regards to their interest and strengths as a student. Also, an environment that supports and encourages your individual growth and development is indeed a key aspect of a good home learning environment. When your parents are aware of your interests and strengths, they can provide the necessary resources, guidance, and opportunities to help you thrive academically and personally. By recognizing student strengths, parents can provide guidance and support in areas where you excel. They can help you set goals, explore related opportunities, and connect you with mentors or resources that can further enhance your skills and knowledge. Also, identifying your strengths as a learner allows parents to identify and nurture any talents you may have. Whether it's in academics, arts, sports, or any other domain, they can provide the necessary support and encouragement to help you develop and showcase your talents. Moreover, when parents acknowledge and appreciate student's strengths and interests, it boosts your self-confidence and self-esteem. It reinforces the belief that you have unique abilities and talents, which can have a positive impact on their overall well-being and academic performance.

On the other hand, the indicator 5 “My parents always assist/guide me in my assignments or projects” had the lowest mean of 3.40 and interpreted as Experienced. Such indicator had received the lowest mean probably due to the conflicting and demanding work schedules of most parents that this hinders them to not have sufficient time to be spent with their family especially in guiding their children in their learning and supporting them as well, thus, generally affecting their parent-child interactions along the way. It is also noted that the respondents are grade six pupils already which was expected by the parents to be independent in doing their assignment and projects. Some of them are instructed to create their own assignment and projects thus refusing to ask for help from their parents. Parental assistance can be valuable in the short term, but it is essential for students to gradually take ownership of their academic work. While parental assistance can be beneficial, there is a risk of students becoming overly reliant on their parents. If students constantly rely on their parents for help, they may not develop the independence and problem-solving skills necessary for academic success in the long run. That's why as students' progress through their education, they should develop the ability to work independently and apply critical thinking skills without relying solely on parental guidance.

The overall weighted mean for parent-child interactions was 3.51 and interpreted as Highly Experienced. This interprets that, with regards to establishing or nurturing parent-child interactions, this is mostly manifested by having the parents effectively identify the interests and strengths of their children as learners and help them sustain and nourish them. When your parents acknowledge and appreciate your strengths and interests, it boosts your self-confidence and self-esteem. It reinforces the belief that you have unique abilities and talents, which can have a positive impact on your overall well-being and academic performance. Regularly sharing thoughts and aspiration with their parents and keeping them informed about their child's interest is a sign of open and strong communication as it is essential in fostering a healthy and good home learning environment. It's important to strike a balance between parental assistance and fostering student independence. To add, understanding student's interests and strengths allows parents to tailor educational experiences to match student's unique learning style. They can incorporate activities, materials, and resources that align with your interests, making learning more engaging and enjoyable for you. Also, they pursue subjects or activities that align with their interests, they are more likely to be motivated and engaged in your learning. Their parents can help

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

them explore and delve deeper into those areas, fostering a love for learning and encouraging them to take ownership of their education. However, parents should aim to empower their children to become self-reliant learners, gradually reducing their involvement as the student gains skills and confidence.

Children are more likely to do well in school and have better social and emotional development when their parents are active in their education. Student achievement, self-esteem, and behavior improve when parents are involved and it also aids in the development of strong relationships between parents and their child's school (Llego, 2019). As such, according to Wang et al. (2020) when parents and children collaborate on educational initiatives, they spend more time together, which deepens their bond. In such cases, parents can provide solace through conversations and interactions with their children, which may help them feel less uneasy and uncomfortable and it has also been advised that parents be taught ways for emotionally supporting their children during difficult times, especially regarding their learning.

Table.3. Student-Respondent Experience on Home Learning Environment in Terms of Learning Materials

Learning Materials	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. I have a copy of our lesson to review at home	3.79	0.53	Highly Experienced
2. I use online copies of our lessons, modules	3.28	0.50	Experienced
3. I use available book and textbooks	3.74	0.45	Highly Experienced
4. I read or use printed copies of our lessons, modules	3.53	0.50	Highly Experienced
5. I use other tools or technology-based in learning	3.38	0.53	Experienced
MEAN	3.54	0.25	Highly Experienced
Legend:	Range of Means	Verbal Interpretation	
	3.50 – 4.00	Highly Experienced	
	2.50 – 3.49	Experienced	
	1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Experienced	
	1.00 – 1.49	Never Experienced	

As shown in the findings presented in Table 3, with regards to the student-respondent experience home learning environment in terms of learning materials, it can be seen that the indicator 1 “I have a copy of our lesson to review at home” gained the highest mean of 3.79 and interpreted as Highly Experienced. Learning materials, despite the advent of the digital age is still considered to be an important part of learning and thus, it is possible that having a copy of the day’s lessons are considered essential by the respondents as this can allow them to have a physical copy of their lesson and at the same time, can allow them to have the opportunity to review and increase their learning with the help of other resources and also that of their parents or guardians. Also, most of the teacher ask the student to copy their lesson that day or jot down note so that they can ensure that they have lecture to review and study during test. Moreover, having a copy of your lesson to review at home can be very beneficial for student’s learning. It allows to reinforce what have learned in class, clarify any doubts or questions if they have, and study at their own pace. Creating a good home learning environment is important for academic performance, and having the necessary materials, such as lesson notes, readily available is a step in the right direction.

On the other hand, the indicator 2 “I use online copies of our lessons, modules” had the lowest mean of 3.28 and was verbally interpreted as Experienced. Despite the continued use of different digital devices in learning, it is still quite surprising that not that many students are keen in utilizing online copies of their lessons and modules. This could probably be associated with the amount or tendency of distraction that they can encounter in viewing their lessons or modules in their devices and can take up the time they allocated instead for studying or reviewing at home. On the other hand, internet connection is one factor affecting this result since not all students have internet connection at home or if they have it’s not strong enough to open a document file. Moreover, gadgets available at home is another factor to look into since most of the student do not have a personal computer or laptop at home. They only have a cellphone but most of them where not compatible to view such documents like module in pdf file.

Furthermore, the overall mean for learning materials was 3.54 and interpreted also as Highly Experienced. As such, this interprets that in terms of learning materials, this is mostly being done with the learners' access to the needed copies of their lessons and modules and their adequate availability to be helpful in their learning. If students have the available materials at home, it can have several implications, First, is accessibility. Having materials at home ensures that students have easy access to resources they need for their studies. They can refer to textbooks, reference books, and other educational materials whenever required, without depending solely on school or library resources. Also, when students have the necessary materials at home, they can engage in continuous learning beyond the classroom. They can explore topics of interest, conduct additional research, or review and revise concepts they have learned in school. Additionally, students have materials at home, parents can also play a more active role in their education. They can assist with homework, provide additional explanations, and engage in discussions related to the subjects being studied. Students can use the available materials to prepare for upcoming lessons or exams. They can preview the content, familiarize themselves with new topics, and be better prepared to participate actively in classroom discussions. But it is important to note that

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

while having materials at home can be beneficial, it should not replace the role of schools, teachers, and other educational resources. A well-rounded education requires a combination of in-school learning experiences, peer interactions, and guidance from educators. Betlen (2021) indicated that the primary knowledge that students will encounter, acquire, and apply during a course is provided by instructional materials, and they have the capacity to either engage or demotivate pupils. Instructional resources are important because they assist teachers and students in avoiding an overemphasis on recitation and rote learning, which may easily dominate a session. Moreover, resource materials provide learners with hands-on experiences that help them acquire skills and concepts and work in a number of ways. Having access to a variety of resources can enhance the learning experience and facilitate a deeper understanding of the subject matter. Learning materials, such as textbooks, online resources, videos, and interactive tools, provide comprehensive and organized content that covers the essential topics and concepts of a subject. They can offer different perspectives and explanations, making it easier for learners to grasp complex ideas. Also, learning materials often include practice exercises, quizzes, and assignments that allow learners to reinforce their understanding through active engagement. Regular practice with relevant learning materials can help solidify knowledge and improve retention. Moreover, people have different learning styles and preferences. Some may learn better through visual aids, while others prefer reading or hands-on activities. The availability of diverse learning materials caters to these different styles, enabling learners to engage with the content in a way that suits them best. To add, learning materials that are accessible outside of the traditional classroom setting empower learners to study at their own pace. They can revisit concepts, review lessons, and delve deeper into topics of interest. This flexibility promotes personalized learning and allows learners to focus on areas where they need more practice or clarification.

Table 4. Student-Respondent Experience of Parent-Teacher Ecology as to Similarity in Cultures and Values

Culture and Values	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. My parents and teacher show positive behavior about my studies	3.62	0.49	Highly Experienced
2. My parents and teacher discipline me concerning my studies	3.66	0.48	Highly Experienced
3. My parents and teacher teach moral values	3.72	0.45	Highly Experienced
4. My parents and teacher always remind us of good values	3.89	0.32	Highly Experienced
5. My parents and teacher always connect lessons to moral lessons	3.75	0.43	Highly Experienced
MEAN	3.73	0.23	Highly Experienced

Legend:	Range of Means	Verbal Interpretation
3.50 – 4.00	Highly Experienced	
2.50 – 3.49	Experienced	
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Experienced	
1.00 – 1.49	Never Experienced	

Based from the findings presented in Table 4, in connection to the student-respondent experience parent-teacher ecology as to similarity in cultures and values, the indicator 4 “My parents and teacher always remind us of good values” had gained the highest mean of 3.89 and interpreted as Highly Experienced. Improved parent-teacher relationships are important to be established in order for both parents and teacher to maximize their knowledge and skills to help the students to learn and it is possible that the way in which parents and teacher reiterates good values is that this is considered to be equally important as in terms of gaining knowledge and skills and is believed that can help learners to be better people in the future. Besides, parents and teachers were always considered by students who look up to them that’s why they usually perceived good values from them.

Cultivating and promoting positive values is essential for personal growth and building a harmonious society. When parents and teachers align in their approach, it reinforces the messages children receive and helps shape their character and behavior. Consistency between home and school environments creates a sense of stability and reinforces the values being taught. It allows children to see that the principles they learn at school are not limited to the classroom but are also valued and practiced within their family. This alignment also helps in reinforcing positive habits and attitudes, as children observe that the same expectations and standards are upheld in different areas of their lives.

On the other hand, the indicator 1 “My parents and teacher show positive behavior about my studies” had the lowest mean of 3.62 and interpreted as Highly Experienced as well. Even though it got the lowest mean it still implies that both teacher and parents show positive behavior with regards to their studies. Having supportive parents and teachers who show positive behavior towards your studies can have a significant impact on your academic performance and overall well-being. It's important to have a strong support system in your educational journey.

With this result, it typically means that they are encouraging, motivating, and recognizing the efforts and achievements of students. This positive reinforcement can boost self-confidence, increase motivation to learn, and create a positive attitude towards studies. Positive reinforcement from your parents and teacher can boost your motivation and confidence in your academic abilities. When they express belief in your potential and appreciate your efforts, you are more likely to feel encouraged to work hard and strive for

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

success. In class, when students receive positive feedback and support, it enhances their academic performance. The belief that your parents and teacher have in you can inspire you to set higher goals, put in extra effort, and engage more actively in your studies, leading to better results. Positive behavior from your parents and teacher creates a supportive and nurturing environment, which contributes to your emotional well-being. Feeling valued and supported in your educational journey can reduce stress, anxiety, and feelings of inadequacy, allowing you to focus more on learning and personal growth. When your parents and teacher show enthusiasm and interest in your studies, it can foster a sense of engagement and passion for learning. Their positive behavior can make your educational experience more enjoyable and meaningful, motivating you to explore subjects further and develop a lifelong love for learning.

The overall mean for similarity in cultures and values was 3.73 and interpreted as Highly Experienced. As such, this interprets that similarity in cultures and values is mostly seen in the way in which both teachers and parents tend to exemplify and reiterate the importance of good values and how they should be integrated into their daily lives through their learning. Moreover, children learn by example, so it's important for parents and teachers to embody the values they promote. Demonstrating these values through their own actions and interactions with others sets a powerful example for children to follow. Overall, when parents and teachers share and reinforce good values, it creates a strong foundation for children's development, shaping them into responsible, empathetic, and morally conscious individuals. Positive behavior regarding your studies can deepen your bond with your parents and teacher. It creates an open line of communication, trust, and mutual respect, as they actively participate in your academic progress. This positive relationship can extend beyond your studies and contribute to your overall development and well-being. It's important to note that while positive behavior from your parents and teacher can have numerous benefits, it's equally crucial to cultivate intrinsic motivation and a genuine passion for learning. Balancing external encouragement with internal drive can lead to a well-rounded approach to education and personal growth.

In such aspect, this can be connected to the work of Der Wal (2020) who noted that affective quality of the home-school connection as parent-teacher relationship quality is usually measured by factors such as trust, mutuality, affiliation, support, shared values, and expectations and beliefs about each other and the learner or student. It has been established that the implementation and engagement in such strategies by both parents and teachers improves student growth, lowers student misbehavior, reiterate important life values and also increases lesson efficiency in a well-managed classroom environment. Effective collaboration between educators and parents has become increasingly vital in meeting the fundamental needs of pupils, as most educators are reacting to increased professional demands, economic obstacles, time constraints, and rapid change. Parents provide their children with their earliest learning experiences, which include feeding, sitting, walking, kindergarten coloring, writing, and reading, among other things.

Table 5. Student-Respondent Experience of Parent-Teacher Ecology as to Changes in Family and School Settings

Changes in Family and School Settings	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. Improved interactions with one another in the family or at school	3.64	0.48	Highly Experienced
2. Use technology to connect with one another	3.38	0.53	Experienced
3. Daily communication with one another	3.55	0.50	Highly Experienced
4. Involvement in different events in the home or in school	3.57	0.50	Highly Experienced
5. Appearance of problems and misunderstandings	3.28	0.53	Experienced
Mean	3.48	0.26	Experienced

Legend:	Range of Means	Verbal Interpretation
3.50 – 4.00	Highly Experienced	
2.50 – 3.49	Experienced	
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Experienced	
1.00 – 1.49	Never Experienced	

Based from the findings presented in Table 5, in connection to the student-respondent experience parent-teacher ecology as to changes in family and school settings, the indicator 1 “Improved interactions with one another in the family or at school” had the highest mean of 3.64 and was verbally interpreted as Highly Experienced. It is possible that having or establishing improved connections or interactions within the family and school was positively viewed by the learners as these settings have an influence on the way the behavior and attitude of learners are being formed towards their learning and the amount of support that they are getting from these settings also plays a significant role in their continued motivation to learn and improve themselves. Improved interactions among family members and between parents and teachers can indeed be seen as a sign of a positive parent-teacher ecology. When there is a healthy and collaborative relationship between parents and teachers, it often translates into better communication, support, and understanding, both at home and in the school environment. To add, parents and teachers regularly exchange information about the child's progress, behavior, and any concerns. They communicate through various channels like emails, parent-teacher meetings, or phone calls. This open dialogue helps in addressing issues promptly and working together to support the child. Also, when parents and teachers respect each other's expertise and contribution and they trust each other's

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

judgment and work collaboratively to make decisions it resulted to the best interest of the child. This positive regard fosters a supportive environment where everyone feels valued and heard.

As such, the indicator 5 “Appearance of problems and misunderstandings” had the lowest mean of 3.28 and interpreted as Experienced. This can be interpreted those problems and misunderstanding in school and home setting is common and inevitable. Some problems that they may encounter were unsupportive learning environment and poor communication with teachers. A student's ability to concentrate and focus on their studies may be hampered by a disruptive or unsupportive learning environment. It can also infer that sometimes parents and teachers may have different perspectives on what is best for the child. They may prioritize different aspects of the child's development or have different educational philosophies. These differences can lead to misunderstandings or conflicts when discussing the child's progress, disciplinary measures, or academic approaches. There are also instances that parents and teacher have the different way they discipline their child. Some parents were very sensitive in accepting the attitude or behavior of their child. There are also parents who are in denial on how their child behave in school thus resulting to conflict and problems between parents and teachers.

The overall mean for changes in family and school settings was 3.48 and interpreted as Experienced. This interprets those certain changes in family and school settings are evident and inevitable, and this was mostly seen by the learners as having improved interactions with one another not just in their family but also in their family or home environment, which can have a significant positive impact on their learning experience. However, with the rising of problems and misunderstanding which is very common with parents and teachers we can address thru promoting effective communication and collaboration between parents and teachers. By fostering an environment of open communication, empathy, and collaboration, many problems and misunderstandings can be addressed and resolved more effectively, ultimately benefiting the child's development and success in both the family and school settings. Alterations in school and home environments can affect academic performance. Problems and changes in both setting can also affect social and emotional development of student. School and home settings play crucial roles in shaping a child's social and emotional development.

According to Younas et al. (2020), the academic achievement of early learners necessitates exceptional tutoring, as requested by parents, educators, and other stakeholders. Given this, one of the most important factors impacting pupils' performance and academic achievement is their family environment as well as in their school. Several researchers also explored the development of positivity as one of several learning experiences that should be researched as part of proactive youth development. Learners are rarely given the opportunity to learn initiative, despite the fact that it is essential for adults in society and will become even more so in the twenty-first century. This lends credence to the link between school involvement, achievement, and conduct and the degree of economic and social strengths and weaknesses. As a result, parents bear the most obligation and accountability for educating their children on a variety of moral, ethical, behavioral, and adaptive levels. They provide both necessities and comforts of life in order to stimulate cognitive development for speedy educational achievement. Several studies have looked at numerous characteristics such as the parents' educational history, job, and personal income and discovered that children with financially stable parents can do well in school.

While children’s learning and development are of primary concern and concentration in the relationships between families and educators, children also deserve to be involved in the planning and decisions that affect their learning. Therefore, school-family partnerships need to be considered through the lens of a learning community that acknowledges the unique contributions from three key players—the teacher, the parent, and the child (Zhang, 2015). Successful learning communities are dynamic and complex webs of relationships based on socially and culturally responsive collaboration, negotiation, understanding, and cooperation, within which school-family partnerships operate. Learning and teaching are social experiences that take place in a context consisting of social expectations, cultural values, and relationships between people that directly impacts learning and development

Table 6. Student-Respondent Experiences on Parent-Teacher Ecology as to View of Scope and Function

View of Scope and Function	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. Going to work daily to earn to support the family	3.58	0.60	Highly Experienced
2. Reminding daily the important values in life	3.79	0.41	Highly Experienced
3. Fulfilling their responsibilities as parents to their children	3.66	0.48	Highly Experienced
4. Attending or supporting different home or school events	3.74	0.45	Highly Experienced
5. Spending some time to improve or discover skills or hobbies	3.60	0.49	Highly Experienced
Mean	3.68	0.28	Highly Experienced

Legend:	Range of Means	Verbal Interpretation
3.50 – 4.00	Highly Experienced	
2.50 – 3.49	Experienced	
1.50 – 2.49	Slightly Experienced	
1.00 – 1.49	Never Experienced	

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

Based from the findings presented in Table 6, in connection to the student-respondent experience parent-teacher ecology as to view of scope and function, the indicator 2 “Reminding daily the important values in life” had the highest mean of 3.79 and interpreted as Highly Experienced. This particular result can be indicated to influence the view of scope and function of parents and teachers, and such can be manifested in the way in which both parents and teachers, in their respective ways, are incorporating the significance of values in life wherein in teachers, this is mostly seen in the morals of their lessons and among parents, in terms of real-life application. As parents and teachers, it is important to constantly remind ourselves of the important values in life and our roles in shaping the lives of children. Both parents and teachers play a vital role in teaching children to respect themselves and others. Parents instill this value by modeling respectful behavior at home, while teachers reinforce it through classroom rules and respectful interactions with students and peers. To add, they both display the sense of responsibility since parents and teachers share the responsibility of teaching children to be responsible individuals. Parents can encourage responsibility by assigning age-appropriate chores and tasks, while teachers can do the same in the classroom through assignments and group projects that promote accountability.

On the other hand, the indicator 1 “Going to work daily to earn for support the family” had the lowest mean of 3.58 and both verbally interpreted as Highly Experienced. As such, it can be interpreted that even though it got the lowest mean it is still evident. Working daily to support your family is a responsible and important task. It shows dedication and a strong sense of responsibility. Also, it is clearly seen that the scope and function of parents and teachers extend beyond teaching values and shaping character; they also have important roles in supporting the family through their work. By fulfilling their roles as providers and educators, parents and teachers contribute to the overall stability and well-being of families. Working diligently to support the family's financial needs and imparting essential life skills, they play a crucial part in shaping children into responsible and independent individuals who can contribute positively to society.

The overall mean for view of scope and function was 3.68 and interpreted as Highly Experienced as well. Further, this interprets that with regards to the scope and function of both parents and teachers, this is mostly concerned with knowing their responsibilities, and this is mostly done by working daily in order to earn for the family and support their needs, particularly in their education. When parents and teachers are aware of each other's roles, they can reinforce important lessons and skills consistently. This consistency in expectations, discipline, and academic guidance can help the child develop a strong foundation and a structured approach to learning. Parents and teachers together can promote the holistic development of the child, recognizing that education extends beyond academics. They can collaborate to nurture the child's social, emotional, and behavioral skills, fostering a well-rounded growth that goes beyond the classroom. Moreover, when they are actively engaged in the child's education, it sends a powerful message that education is valued and important. This involvement can motivate the child to take their studies seriously and develop a positive attitude towards learning. Hence, strong partnership between parents and teachers creates a supportive learning environment where the child feels secure and encouraged. This atmosphere can enhance the child's overall well-being, self-esteem, and motivation, leading to improved academic performance. Overall, when parents and teachers understand their respective roles and collaborate effectively, it can create a powerful synergy that benefits the child's educational journey, leading to better outcomes and holistic development.

As such, according to Faaz (2017) the level of education of parents and students in strong financial standing clearly differs from one another. The term "home environment" refers to a child's family background, which comprises all people and material resources in the home that influence the child's capacity to live independently, such as the parent's financial condition, level of education, and employment. It also relates to how the family interacts with the facilities of the house. To add, the teacher's function is limited to the classroom, but the parent's function applies to all facets of the child's life. Teachers are in charge of all the kids for a defined amount of time when they are at school, therefore their job is more objective, detached, and logical. They help each kid individually with their knowledge, skills, and talents. Parental relationships, on the other hand, are shaped by their own child for whom they are responsible 24 hours a day and are likely to exhibit intense partiality, attachment, and even irrationality in their interactions about their own child (Keyes, 2020). The teacher's role is shaped by professional knowledge about "all children." As partnerships are formed, it is crucial to search for the places of convergence given the differences in roles.

Table 7. Perceived Academic Performance of Pupils in Terms of Academic Achievement

Academic Achievement	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. I can read smoothly and with comprehension	3.70	0.46	Excellent
2. I can ask question and contribute to the class discussion	3.51	0.54	Excellent
3. I prepare myself in all my subjects	3.77	0.42	Excellent
4. I am able to pass my tests or examinations	3.53	0.50	Excellent
5. I enjoy homework and activities because they help me improve my skills in every subject	3.75	0.43	Excellent
Mean	3.65	0.25	Excellent

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

Legend:	Range of Means	Verbal Interpretation
3.50 – 4.00	Excellent	
2.50 – 3.49	Good	
1.50 – 2.49	Average	
1.00 – 1.49	Poor	

Further, as based from the findings presented in Table 7, with regards to the academic performance of pupils in terms of academic achievement, the indicator 3 “I prepare myself in all my subjects” had the highest mean of 3.77 and was verbally interpreted as Excellent. The possible reason on why preparations made for all subjects gained the highest mean with regards to academic achievement is that learners think that as long as they are well-prepared in their subjects, this can allow them to perform well and also participate more in various activities that they will be having in class and can also allow them to achieve high scores in their tests or examinations. Moreover, they believed that if they prepare more in all my subject, they will be more advanced from their classmate thus making them excel in class. Also, preparing yourself in all your subjects is indeed a sign of dedication and commitment to academic achievement. It demonstrates your willingness to put in the effort and time required to excel in your studies.

On the other hand, the indicator 2 “I can ask question and contribute to the class discussion” had the lowest mean of 3.51 and interpreted also as Excellent. Participating actively in class discussions and asking insightful questions is indeed considered a sign of academic achievement. Engaging in discussions not only demonstrates your understanding of the material but also shows your curiosity and critical thinking skills. With this result, we can say that actively participating in class allows students to engage with the material in a more interactive and dynamic way. By asking questions, contributing to discussions, and sharing of thoughts, students actively process and reinforce the information. This can lead to a deeper understanding of the subject matter and improved retention of knowledge. To add active participation in class discussion is a way of developing critical thinking skills, engaging in class discussions helps develop critical thinking skills. By analyzing concepts, evaluating arguments, and formulating thoughtful responses, you learn to think more critically and engage in higher-level cognitive processes. This skill is valuable not only in academic settings but also in various real-life situations.

The overall weighted mean for academic achievement was 3.65 and also interpreted as Excellent. This interprets that academic achievement for the learners or pupils was more concerned with being able to prepare adequately for the subjects that they have in class, which can enable them to do well and participate in the day’s activities ahead of them. Also, actively participating in class discussions demonstrate enthusiasm for learning, critical thinking abilities, and willingness to engage with the subject matter. This engagement can contribute to your academic achievement and enhance your overall learning experience. By being prepared, learners can make the most of their educational experience and maximize their learning opportunities. It allows them to absorb and retain information more effectively, apply knowledge to real-world situations, and develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Preparedness also enhances learners' confidence in their abilities, which can positively impact their motivation, engagement, and overall academic performance. Furthermore, active participation in class helps learners to deepen their understanding of the subjects, clarify doubts, and develop communication and collaboration skills. By actively engaging in discussions and activities, learners can exchange ideas, gain different perspectives, and build connections between concepts. This interactive learning environment fosters a deeper level of learning and can contribute to improved academic achievement.

If a student is unprepared, he/she may fail an assignment or a class, which causes stress and pessimism and only serves to exacerbate academic problems and thus, it is essential instead, on taking proactive control of the educational experience before it begins can assist a student in building good momentum from the start (Kokemuller, 2019). As such, it was also added by Roemmich et al. (2006) home facilities of environment for children both allow and hinder them from engaging in educational activities at home. Because children only spend five to six hours a day at school and the rest of their time at home, it is critical that they prepare for class and practice at home.

Table 8. Perceived Academic Performance of Pupils in Terms of Persistence

Parent-Child Interaction	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. I attend all of my classes	3.64	0.48	Excellent
2. I can finish the assigned tasks or activities	3.72	0.45	Excellent
3. I can answer my teacher’s questions	3.70	0.46	Excellent
4. I pay attention and listen during every discussion	3.77	0.42	Excellent
5. I am struggling but I can cope	3.49	0.54	Good
Mean	3.66	0.25	Excellent

Legend:	Range of Means	Verbal Interpretation
3.50 – 4.00	Excellent	
2.50 – 3.49	Good	

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

1.50 – 2.49	Average
1.00 – 1.49	Poor

Further, as based from the findings presented in Table 8, with regards to the academic performance of pupils in terms of persistence, the indicator 4 “I pay attention and listen during every discussion” gained the highest mean of 3.77 and was verbally interpreted as Excellent. As such, it can be interpreted that paying attention and listening to every discussion being conducted in class was considered as a proof of persistence of the learners may be related on the notion that listening and paying attention in class usually requires a lot of patience and restraint to converse instead with their classmates and remained distracted in the duration of the class. Students' academic achievement is heavily reliant on their ability to pay attention in class. Students' attention enables them to tune out irrelevant material, background noise, visual distractions, and even their own thoughts. This allows students to concentrate and focus on the crucial information provided by the teachers. Actively listening during discussions can lead to improved productivity. By paying attention, the person can better understand instructions, tasks, and goals, reducing the chances of miscommunication or misunderstandings. This can contribute to more efficient collaboration and better outcomes in various contexts, such as work or group projects. This result implies that the students value active engagement, respects others, strives for effective communication, seeks learning opportunities, possesses strong interpersonal skills, and aims for increased productivity.

On the other hand, the indicator 5 “I am struggling but I can cope” had the lowest mean of 3.49 and interpreted as Good. As such, this interprets that resilience or the ability to cope while facing some struggles is not that much yet developed among the learners. Persistence can be developed through proper resilience and teachers and parents should be aware of its importance and their role in ensuring that they can be able to impart to the students the value of resilience and how it can help them to get over the various challenges that they face while learning. According to Aun et al. (2011), coping skills boost class attendance, participation, tenacity even when faced with setbacks or failure in general, and arm students with a stronger, more resilient self, which can lead to a far more positive learning experience. Similarly, academic coping methods aided undergraduate students in their academic performance by utilizing academic coping strategy components such as approach, avoidance, and social support.

The overall weighted mean for persistence was 3.66 and interpreted as Excellent. In fact, this interprets that, with regards to the aspect of persistence, this was mostly manifested or exhibited by the pupils in terms of providing their best attention to their teachers and listening attentively in every discussion to keep up in their classes. Persistence in listening during discussions enables students to overcome challenges in their studies. Sometimes, certain topics or concepts may be difficult to grasp initially, but by consistently paying attention and actively listening, it increases the chances of understanding and overcoming those challenges. It demonstrates willingness to persevere through difficulties and work towards achieving your academic goals. Moreover, paying attention and actively listening during discussions are clear indicators of persistence in student studies. It showcases student’s dedication to learning, improves comprehension and retention, enables effective participation, builds relationships, and helps overcome challenges. By consistently applying these behaviors, students can enhance their academic performance and achieve greater success in studies.

Such ability and persistence being displayed by the learners can be related to the way they are being attended to in their respective homes. As such, the house serves as a playground, art studio, library, and laboratory for the youngsters. In their homes, children begin their first studies in literacy, arithmetic, science, art, and music. At home, children build and test some of their initial assumptions about how the world works, gradually honing both their knowledge and abilities as well as their learning expectations, beliefs, goals, and methods. As a result, it has long been assumed that the family environment plays an important part in shaping how children develop, even though the majority of academics today reject socialization models that pay little attention to genetics and the ways in which children impact their families (Norman, 2020).

Table 9. Perceived Academic Performance of Pupils in Terms of Attainment of Learning Outcomes

Attainment of Learning Outcomes	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. I can pass a test/quiz in class	3.58	0.50	Excellent
2. I am able to think clearly and make decisions	3.53	0.54	Excellent
3. I can understand or comprehend texts or lessons	3.60	0.49	Excellent
4. I am able to share my knowledge with others	3.57	0.54	Excellent
5. I have been able to improve my skills and other interests	3.74	0.45	Excellent
Mean	3.60	0.26	Excellent

Legend:	Range of Means	Verbal Interpretation
3.50 – 4.00	Excellent	
2.50 – 3.49	Good	
1.50 – 2.49	Average	
1.00 – 1.49	Poor	

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

Based from the findings presented in Table 9, with regards to the academic performance of pupils in terms of attainment of learning outcomes, the indicator 5 “I have been able to improve my skills and other interests” had the highest mean of 3.74 and interpreted as Excellent. It can be noted that academic performance was mostly seen by the learners as having the opportunity or proof for them to improve on their respective skills and interests. As such, academic performance cannot only be measured by how well the students are doing in class but also the way in which they can be able to apply what they had learned in terms of solving real-life problems. Moreover, improving skills and pursuing other interests are valuable aspects of attaining learning outcomes. When you focus on developing your skills and exploring different interests, you can enhance your personal growth, broaden your knowledge, and increase your overall effectiveness in various areas of life.

The other indicator 2 “I am able to think clearly and make decisions” had the lowest mean of 3.53 and verbally interpreted as Excellent. This particular finding is understandable since it is still interpreted as evident to most students as well mainly because thinking clearly or logically and making sound and right decisions can be considered as a sign of academic performance. Clear thinking and effective decision-making are certainly important skills that can positively impact academic performance. When you are able to think clearly, you can process information more efficiently, analyze problems effectively, and come up with logical solutions. This clarity of thought allows you to grasp complex concepts, connect ideas, and develop a deeper understanding of the subjects you're studying. The ability to think clearly and make decisions can be seen as an indicator of attaining learning outcomes in many educational settings. When learners can demonstrate clear thinking and effective decision-making skills, it suggests that they have acquired and internalized the knowledge, understanding, and skills taught within a particular learning context. Making decisions based on what has been learned demonstrates the ability to apply knowledge and skills in real-world situations. Learners who can think critically and make appropriate decisions are likely to be able to transfer what they have learned to new contexts. Also, decision-making is an essential aspect of problem-solving. When learners can think clearly and make effective decisions, they are better equipped to identify problems, evaluate different solutions, and select the most appropriate course of action.

The overall weighted mean for the attainment of learning outcomes was 3.60 and also interpreted as Always. As such, this interprets that the attainment of learning outcomes was mostly achieved by allowing the students to have plenty of opportunities that can help them improve their skills and how these skills can effectively contribute to pursuing their respective interests in life. Moreover, learning outcomes often build upon one another, forming a foundation for future academic endeavors. Each outcome is designed to provide the necessary knowledge and skills for the next level of education. By achieving these outcomes, students develop a solid base upon which to build their further learning

Attaining learning outcomes is crucial for academic performance because it directly reflects a student's ability to meet the goals and objectives set by the educational institution or curriculum. Also, learning outcomes serve as benchmarks for assessing a student's progress and understanding of the subject matter. By achieving the expected outcomes, students demonstrate their mastery of the knowledge, skills, and competencies outlined by the curriculum.

According to Brew, et al (2021), a human being's whole existence is frequently determined by the quantity of information he or she accumulates and how much of that knowledge is used to the advancement of the individual, the nation, and the entire globe. This provides the justification for the requirement for education. Knowledge is the fundamental thing that one gains from school. One learns about a variety of subjects, from political science to literature to mathematics. The global information we acquire via school has a significant impact on our future and enables us to comprehend events in a way that is much more coherent. While student academic achievement serves as a gauge of educational accomplishment. Researchers and educators have long been curious about the factors that influence how well students do academically. Academic success is influenced by a variety of variables, such as parents' education and economic levels, teachers' subject-matter expertise, truancy, textbook accessibility and availability, libraries, practical lab, lunch supply, and many other variables. Academic achievement has been found to be significantly influenced by the family environment. Children who live in poverty could be exposed to less stimulating settings and educational opportunities. Secondary school education is meant to be the cornerstone and starting point for higher learning in postsecondary institutions.

Table 10. Positive Social Behavior of Pupils in Terms of Peer Relations

Peer Relations	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. I cooperate with other students	3.72	0.45	Always
2. I understand problems and needs of other students	3.57	0.50	Always
3. I have skills or abilities that are admired by peers	3.49	0.50	Often
4. I give in or compromise with peers when appropriate	3.55	0.50	Always
5. I interact with a wide variety of peers	3.45	0.50	Often
MEAN	3.55	0.29	Always

Legend:	Range of Means	Verbal Interpretation
3.50 – 4.00	Always (High Positive Behavior)	
2.50 – 3.49	Often (Moderate Positive Behavior)	
1.50 – 2.49	Seldom (Low Positive Behavior)	
1.00 – 1.49	Never (Not Positive Behavior)	

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

As seen in Table 10, in connection to the positive social behavior of pupils in terms of peer relations, it can be seen that the indicator 1 “I cooperate with other students” had gained the highest mean of 3.72 and interpreted as Always. This interprets that in terms of developing the positive social behavior of learners was mostly seen to be manifested in the way in which they can be able to cooperate with their classmates. Cooperation still remained to be a primary indicator of positive social behavior of pupils and this can be improved continuously through the help of both parents and teachers to integrate the development of positive social behavior in lessons and activities in class. This is usually seen during group activities, pair-up activity and even in classroom forums. Most students who are shy in class recitation are very active in cooperating in group activity thus implying that they have positive behavior towards others.

Cooperative learning encourages social relationships; therefore, students benefit in a variety of ways from a social standpoint. Cooperative learning promotes oral communication abilities by having students explain their thinking and conclusions. Cooperation among students is indeed a positive social behavior that can have numerous benefits. When students engage in cooperation, they work together towards a common goal, pooling their skills, knowledge, and resources. However, cooperation promotes a collaborative learning environment where students can share ideas, perspectives, and insights. Through cooperative activities, students can learn from one another, clarify concepts, and develop a deeper understanding of the subject matter. In addition to these, cooperation encourages students to tackle challenges collectively, fostering the development of problem-solving skills. By engaging in discussions and brainstorming sessions, students can explore multiple solutions and learn to think critically.

On the other hand, the indicator 5 “I interact with a wide variety of peers” had the lowest mean obtained of 3.45 and verbally interpreted as Often. As such, this interprets that interacting with students still remained to have its own set of positive and negative impacts and it’s up to parents and teachers to balance it out and explain this to the learners. Since peer interactions are vital in the development of young children, and peer groups are influential in the development of teenage identity. Adolescence is a time when young people seek acceptance and a sense of belonging through peer groups, as they seek an independent identity from their relatives. Interacting with individuals from diverse backgrounds, cultures, and experiences exposes us to different viewpoints and helps broaden our perspective. By not engaging with a wide variety of peers, one may miss out on the opportunity to gain new insights and expand their understanding of the world. Sometime students refuse to interactive with other people with the fear of rejection or lacking of self-confidence. In addition, interacting with a homogeneous group can lead to a limited range of ideas and perspectives. By engaging with peers from various backgrounds, people are exposed to different ways of thinking and problem-solving, which can foster innovation and creativity. Regular interaction with diverse peers helps develop social skills such as effective communication, empathy, and teamwork. By limiting interactions to a narrow group, individuals may miss out on opportunities to develop these essential skills, which can be valuable in personal and professional settings.

The overall mean for peer relations was 3.55 and interpreted as Always. Moreover, this interprets that peer relations were mostly viewed by the learners or pupils as not merely in terms of cooperating with their classmates but are now more focused on also interacting with them even without class activities. We can also infer in that when students work together, they often become more engaged in their learning. Cooperative activities provide opportunities for active participation, encouraging students to contribute their thoughts and actively listen to their peers. This engagement can lead to a more positive and enjoyable learning experience. Also, it is noted that cooperation indeed enhanced communication and social skills. Cooperation necessitates effective communication and interpersonal skills. Through collaborative tasks, students learn to express their ideas, listen attentively to others, provide constructive feedback, and resolve conflicts. These skills are essential for successful collaboration not only in the academic setting but also in various aspects of life.

According to Tullis & Goldstone (2020) children develop a variety of key social emotional skills, such as empathy, cooperation, and problem-solving tactics, in a unique context through peer connections or relations. Bullying, exclusion, and deviant peer practices can all have a negative impact on social emotional development. As a result, learners who participate in peer discussion can apply their new knowledge to solve new but related challenges on their own. Peer instruction significantly helps students' abilities to tackle different problems by means of generating new information and disclosing gaps in knowledge. Overall, cooperation among students is a sign of positive social behavior as it promotes learning, problem-solving, communication, empathy, and respect. Encouraging and fostering a cooperative spirit in the classroom can lead to improved academic outcomes and the development of well-rounded individuals.

Table 11. Positive Social Behavior of Pupils in Terms of Self-Management/Compliance

Self-Management/Compliance	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. I make appropriate transitions between different activities	3.60	0.57	Always
2. I complete schoolwork without being reminded	3.70	0.46	Always.
3. I remain calm when problems arise	3.58	0.50	Always
4. I follow the school and classroom rules	3.79	0.41	Always
5. I behave appropriately at school	3.60	0.49	Always
MEAN	3.66	0.24	Always

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

Legend:	Range of Means	Verbal Interpretation
3.50 – 4.00	Always (High Positive Behavior)	
2.50 – 3.49	Often (Moderate Positive Behavior)	
1.50 – 2.49	Seldom (Low Positive Behavior)	
1.00 – 1.49	Never (Not Positive Behavior)	

As seen in Table 11, in connection to the positive social behavior of pupils in terms of self-management/compliance, it can be seen that the indicator 4 “I follow the school and classroom rules” had the highest mean of 3.79 and verbally interpreted as Always. This particular finding can be noted to indicate how self-management/compliance was mostly manifested by means of following school and classroom rules and that the continued obedience or adherence to these rules by the students only showed that they can be able to practice improved self-management, compliance as well as self-discipline. Self-management and compliance are indeed important aspects of a student's behavior within a school setting. Following school and classroom rules is a fundamental way for students to demonstrate self-management and compliance. By adhering to these rules, students learn to regulate their own behavior, exercise self-control, and contribute to a positive and productive learning environment. To add, this behavior is a solid manifestation of respect for authority. Students who comply with school and classroom rules show respect for the authority figures in their educational environment, such as teachers, administrators, and staff members. They understand the importance of listening to and following instructions given by these individuals. Also, this indicates that the students believed that their teachers were setting standards and expectations in the classroom by frequently reminding the students of what was expected of them. They teach students the rules and procedures for the classroom as well as the allocated responsibilities and tasks in order to build regulations. Teachers are viewed by students as having the power to organize, govern, and make decisions in their classrooms because of their position of authority.

On the other hand, the indicator 3 “I remain calm when problems arise” had the lowest mean of 3.58 and both verbally interpreted as Always. As such, even though it got the lowest mean, its verbal interpretation falls under the highest possible interpretation meaning it is still evident among the respondents. Remaining calm when problems arise is an important skill that can help you effectively navigate challenges and find solution. When you remain calm, your mind is better able to think clearly and rationally. This allows you to assess the situation objectively and make decisions based on logic rather than emotions. You can consider all the available options and choose the best course of action. However, panicking or getting overly anxious in the face of a problem can increase stress levels, which can cloud your judgment and hinder problem-solving. By staying calm, you can reduce stress and maintain a more composed state of mind. This can contribute to better overall well-being and mental health

Further, the overall weighted mean for self-management/compliance was 3.66 and interpreted as Always. This interprets that with regards to the aspect of self-management or compliance, this is mostly concerned with the way in which they can be able to follow school and classroom rules and thus can be considered to be an equally important aspect or part of an improved learning experience for the students. It's important to note that while self-management and compliance are valuable qualities, fostering critical thinking, creativity, and independence should also be encouraged alongside them to support well-rounded development in students.

As previously indicated, rules and regulations are put in place to provide order and standards in the school, and any violation might cause an imbalance. Discipline instills accountability and responsibility in learners as well as teachers who may not be following school policies. Furthermore, in any environment, classroom norms provide the cornerstone for a functional and successful classroom. Rules differ from procedures in that they influence how the classroom appears, what type of behavior is acceptable and promoted, and how students work together to achieve a common goal (Martin, 2022 and Jones, 2018). On the other hand, many of the world's most successful people, including entrepreneurs, sportsmen, and artists, would not have achieved their degree of success if they had not learned how to remain incredibly cool under pressure. They have the ability to establish and sustain a certain state of psychological readiness, which they may call on demand.

Table 12. Positive Social Behavior of Pupils in Terms of Academic Behavior

Academic Behavior	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. I complete school assignments or other tasks independently	3.74	0.45	Always
2. I complete school assignments on time	3.70	0.46	Always
3. I ask for help if needed	3.62	0.53	Always
4. I respond appropriately when corrected by teachers	3.64	0.52	Always
5. I notice and compliment accomplishments of others	3.62	0.49	Always
MEAN	3.66	0.28	Always

Legend:	Range of Means	Verbal Interpretation
3.50 – 4.00	Always (High Positive Behavior)	
2.50 – 3.49	Often (Moderate Positive Behavior)	
1.50 – 2.49	Seldom (Low Positive Behavior)	
1.00 – 1.49	Never (Not Positive Behavior)	

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

As seen in Table 12, in connection to the positive social behavior of pupils in terms of academic behavior, it can be seen that the indicator 1 “I complete school assignments or other tasks independently” gained the highest mean of 3.74 and was verbally interpreted as Always. This interprets that completing school assignments and other tasks independently was seen by the learners as a sign of improved academic behavior. The way in which the learners can finish or submit tasks independently and correctly can be related as a good and disciplined academic behavior as this stems within themselves and exhibiting such responsibility can contribute for them to perform better in their classes and subjects. When learners take the initiative to complete their assignments independently, it shows a sense of responsibility towards their academic work. It indicates that they understand the importance of their studies and are willing to take ownership of their learning. Also, it develops self-discipline. Independent completion of tasks requires self-discipline. It involves setting goals, managing time effectively, and staying focused on the task at hand. When learners develop these skills, it not only benefits their academic performance but also prepares them for future challenges in their personal and professional lives.

On the other hand, the indicators 3 and 5 “I ask for help if needed” and “I notice and compliment accomplishments of others” had the lowest means of 3.62 and was also interpreted as Always consecutively. This interprets that asking for help and offering and acknowledging the achievements of others was still seen as an improved academic behavior since it is still interpreted as Always despite of being the lowest. Recognizing and complimenting the accomplishments of others is a great way to show appreciation and support. It can also help build positive relationships and encourage further success. Compliments can boost someone's self-esteem, motivate them to keep striving, and create a sense of connection and camaraderie. By acknowledging the efforts and achievements of others, you contribute to a positive and uplifting environment.

The overall weighted mean for academic behavior was 3.66 and interpreted as Always. This interprets that, as for academic achievement, this is mostly being displayed or exhibited by the learners in the way that they can be able to complete or submit all their assigned schoolwork, specifically their assignments and tasks, and complete this individually and independently for submission to their teachers. Successfully completing tasks independently can boost learners' confidence in their abilities. It gives them a sense of accomplishment and empowers them to tackle more challenging assignments. This confidence can extend beyond academics and positively impact other areas of their lives. This also promotes personal growth. Independent completion of tasks provides learners with opportunities for personal growth. They learn to rely on their own abilities, make decisions, and overcome obstacles. This process of self-discovery and growth contributes to their overall development as individuals.

Good school behavior and discipline are critical if students are to learn and attain their full potential, and our greatest schools work tirelessly to promote this. Children's learning time can be lost as a result of poor classroom behavior. Improved grades, discipline, time management, resource management, and communication skills are all important life skills that will open the door to new opportunities and help them succeed in their professions (Delfino, 2019). Regular homework completion should be viewed as an investment in your child's future (Santelli et al. 2020). While independent work is important, it's worth noting that collaboration and seeking assistance when needed are also valuable skills. Striking a balance between independent work and collaboration is essential for holistic learning.

Table 13. Positive Social Behavior of Pupils in Terms of Social Competence

A. Parent-Child Interaction		Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1.	I offer help to other students when needed	3.51	0.50	Always
2.	I adjust to different behavioral expectations across settings	3.60	0.49	Always
3.	I respect the wants and dislikes of other people	3.68	0.47	Always
4.	I ask appropriately for clarification of instructions	3.57	0.50	Always
5.	I participate effectively in group discussions and activities	3.70	0.46	Always
MEAN		3.61	0.27	Always
Legend:	Range of Means	Verbal Interpretation		
	3.50 – 4.00	Always (High Positive Behavior)		
	2.50 – 3.49	Often (Moderate Positive Behavior)		
	1.50 – 2.49	Seldom (Low Positive Behavior)		
	1.00 – 1.49	Never (Not Positive Behavior)		

Finally, as seen in Table 13, in connection to the positive social behavior of pupils in terms of social competence, it can be seen that the indicator 5 “I participate effectively in group discussions and activities” had the highest mean of 3.70 and interpreted as Always. Further, this interprets that social competence was mostly being developed and manifested by means of increased participation or engagement of the learners in group discussions and activities in their class. As such, it aids in the learners' ability to forge solid social bonds and collaborate well with others and can also help them to better navigate their way in a complicated and

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

linked environment, and the means by which they can connect better with others will be established. Participating effectively in group discussions and activities is indeed a sign of social competence. It demonstrates your ability to engage with others, communicate your ideas, listen to different perspectives, and collaborate towards common goals. Effective participation can be demonstrated by active listening: Pay attention to what others are saying and show genuine interest. This helps you understand their viewpoints and respond thoughtfully. Avoid interrupting or dominating the conversation. It can also show through respectful communication. Treat others with respect and courtesy. Use inclusive language, avoid personal attacks, and focus on discussing ideas rather than criticizing individuals. Encourage a positive and supportive atmosphere.

On the other hand, the indicator 1 “I offer help to other students when needed” had the lowest mean of 3.51 and was verbally interpreted as Always. Offering help to other students when they need it demonstrates both empathy and social competence. By extending a helping hand, you show that you care about others' well-being and are willing to contribute to their success. This act of kindness can create a positive and supportive atmosphere, fostering a sense of community and collaboration among your peers. Helping others showcases social competence by reflecting qualities such as empathy, effective communication, cooperation, conflict resolution, altruism, leadership, and influence. By continually engaging in acts of support and kindness, you can foster a positive social environment and contribute to the well-being of individuals and communities around you.

The overall mean for social competence was 3.61 and was interpreted as Always. As such, this interprets that social competence is mostly exhibited by being able to help other students when needed, thus improving their social competence along the way. Helping others is indeed a sign of social competence. It reflects various positive qualities and skills that contribute to building healthy relationships and thriving communities. Also helping others can be demonstrated with empathy and perspective-taking: When you help others, you show empathy by understanding and sharing their feelings. You can put yourself in their shoes, which requires perspective-taking and the ability to understand their experiences. This empathy helps you connect with others on a deeper level and build meaningful relationships.

Moreover, according to Fraser (2018) the relevance of the family environment in early childhood literacy and social competency, as well as their eventual school achievement, is widely recognized. The study explored the relationships between family features (such as socioeconomic status (SES), social risk factors, and home learning variables) and children's developing reading competency and social functioning. In addition to this, Sharna (2019) indicated that social competence enables children to connect with peers in a range of settings and contexts, as well as to maintain positive relationships with peers and adults, both of which are essential for academic and life success. As a result, having a strong set of social skills allows a student to interact, relate to, and connect with others, which is vital for forming friendships and navigating life with greater satisfaction.

Table 14. Significant Relationship between the Home Learning Environment to the Academic Performance of Learners

Home Learning Environment	Academic Performance		
	Academic Achievement	Persistence	Attainment of Learning Outcomes
Children’s participation in learning activities;	.404**	.334*	.357**
parent-child interactions; and	.289*	.291*	.365**
learning materials	.088	-.052	.248

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The table 14 displays the significant relationship between home learning environment to the academic performance of learners.

The given data presents the correlation between academic performance in terms of achievement, persistence and attainment of learning outcomes as to children’s participation in learning activities, parent-child interactions; and availability of learning materials.

Based from the findings presented, with regards to the significant relationship between the home learning environment to the academic performance of learners, it can be seen that there is indeed a significant relationship mostly between the children’s participation in learning activities and academic achievement (.404**), with this result it may infer those children who participate actively in class more likely excel and able to achieve the academic objectives. Participating students have learned the content thoroughly enough to explain new ideas to their classmates. This degree of reasoning goes beyond ordinary text comprehension and enhances memory. Additionally, by cooperating with one another, participation can assist students learn from one another and improve comprehension.

Also, there are is significant relationship between children’s participation in class and attainment of learning outcomes (.357**). This may infer that children's involvement in achieving learning objectives is crucial for their general development and academic achievement. Children who actively participate in their education are more motivated, inquisitive, and involved in it.

Moreover, it is also display in the table the significant relationship between attainment of learning outcomes and with parent-child interactions (.365**) The achievement of learning outcomes is significantly influenced by parent-child relationships. Parents may

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

aid in their child's academic achievement and general growth by offering support, direction, reinforcement, and a supportive atmosphere. Together, parents and teachers can lay a solid foundation for children to succeed in their educational endeavors.

On the other hand, learning materials seems to have no significant relationship with academic achievement (.088) and attainment of learning outcomes (.248). Also learning material shows negative relationship with persistence (-.052) as to academic performance.

Overall, from the findings presented in Table 14, with regards to the significant relationship between the home learning environment to the academic performance of learners, it can be seen that there is indeed a significant relationship mostly between the children's participation in learning activities and academic achievement (.404**), attainment of learning outcomes (.357**) and with parent-child interactions (.365**) and thus indicating a significant relationship in these two aspects for academic performance and home learning and partially sustaining the null hypothesis of no significant relationship found.

Table 15. Significant Relationship between the Home Learning Environment to the Social Behavior of Learners

Home Learning Environment	Social Behavior			
	Peer Relation	Self-Management	Academic Behavior	Social Competence
Children's participation in learning activities;	.383**	.447**	.320*	.289*
parent-child interactions; and	.500**	.342*	.185	.315*
learning materials	.092	.175	.020	.033

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The table 15 displays the significant relationship between home learning environment to the social behavior of learners.

The given data presents the correlation between social behavior of learners in terms of peer relation, self-management, academic behavior and social competence as to children's participation in learning activities, parent-child interactions; and availability of learning materials.

Further, based from the findings presented in Table 15, with regards to the significant relationship between the home learning environment to the social behavior of learners, it can be seen that there is indeed a significant relationship mostly between the children's participation in learning activities and peer relations (.383**), it can be interpreted that there is a positive correlation between listening to class and participating in class discussion and understanding the problems of other and interacting with wide variety of peers. By encouraging shared interests, cooperation, common experiences, peer support, socialization, empathy, and understanding, children's active engagement in learning activities can have a good impact on their peer relationships. Children's general social and emotional development can be aided by encouraging them to participate in a variety of learning opportunities.

Also, significant relationship between children's participation in learning activities and self-management (.447**) is very evident. It can also be interpreted that if the students pay attention to the class discussion, they are more likely remain calm if problem arises and followed classroom and school rooms smoothly that clearly shows a positive correlation. Children's involvement in educational activities offers a rich setting for the growth of self-management abilities. Goal-setting, time management, organization, problem-solving, self-regulation, and motivation are some of the diverse topics covered by these abilities. Children can develop these abilities by active participation in educational activities, which is crucial for their general development, academic performance, and personal improvement.

The table also shows significant relationship between children's participation and academic behavior of students (.320*). This shows that if students listen and participate in class discussion, they are more likely to completed school assignments and other task independently and on time. While significant relationship is also evident between children's participating in learning activities and social competence (.289*) which means students who submit journal and worksheet on time are those who participate effectively in group discussion and offer help to others when needed.

Moreover, it is evident that there is in fact a significant relationship between peer relation and with parent-child interactions (.500**). It is important to remember that both parent-child interactions and peer relationships are of utmost importance. In both situations, helpful and uplifting connections tend to have a more beneficial effect on a child's growth. Children are more likely to acquire good social skills, emotional stability, resilience, and a solid foundation for their general development when they have favorable relationships with peers and experience caring and attentive parent-child interactions.

However, the table shows that academic behavior is not affected by parent-child interaction (.185) thus implying of no significant relationship found. It means that student's academic behavior does not rely on parents assisting them in creating assignment, identifying their interest and strengths and even attending in school activities.

On the other hand, we can infer that there is no correlation between learning materials and peer relations (0.92), self-management (.175), academic behavior (.020) and social competence (0.033). In general, there is no significant relationship between learning materials and social behavior of students. It is important to note that while learning materials can influence social behavior to some

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

extent, it is not the sole determinant. Other factors, such as individual personalities, social environment, upbringing, and personal experiences, also play a significant role in shaping social behavior.

Overall, based from the findings presented in Table 15, with regards to the significant relationship between the home learning environment to the social behavior of learners, it can be seen that there is indeed a significant relationship mostly between the children's participation in learning activities and peer relations (.383**), self-management (.447**) and with parent-child interactions (.500**) and thus indicating a significant relationship in these aspects for social behavior and home learning and partially sustaining the null hypothesis of no significant relationship found.

Table 16. Significant Relationship between the Parent-Teacher Ecology to the academic performance of Learners

Parent-Teacher Ecology	Academic Performance		
	Academic Achievement	Persistence	Attainment of Learning Outcomes
Similarity of culture and values;	.320*	.385**	.393**
Changes in family and school settings;	.230	.249	.368**
View of scope and function	.368**	.263	.138

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The table 16 displays the significant relationship between parent-teacher ecology and academic performance of learners.

The given data presents the correlation between academic performance of learners in terms of academic achievement, persistence and attainment of learning outcomes as to similarity of culture and values, changes in family and school settings and view of scope and functions.

As such, based from the findings presented in Table 16, with regards to the significant relationship between parent-teacher ecology to the academic performance of learners, it can be seen that there is indeed a significant relationship mostly between the similarity of culture and values and academic achievement (.320*), so this means that those students who communicate well with parents and teachers are more likely to prepare himself to the class and eventually pass all his/her exam. Also, there is significant relationship between similarity of culture and values and persistence (.385**) Children who actively participate in learning activities become more invested in their education and have a feeling of ownership over it. Their levels of perseverance, which pertain to their capacity to maintain concentration, endure through difficulties, and engage in learning activities, may benefit from their greater engagement. Moreover, Children who actively engage in learning activities foster a culture of perseverance. We can help children build the motivation, practical experiences, social engagement, personalization, acknowledgment of progress, and goal-setting mindsets they need to persevere in their learning and reach their academic objectives.

Also, it can be seen that there is indeed a significant relationship between the similarity of culture and values of parent and teacher and attainment of learning outcomes of students (.393**), When the cultural and values systems of parents and teachers align, it creates a conducive environment for learning and academic performance. This also explains that if the teacher has the same culture and values with regard to child's welfare, they more likely to improve student's knowledge, skills and interest. To add, teachers and parents frequently have comparable expectations for schooling and academic performance when their cultural origins and beliefs are similar. Due to their alignment, they can collaborate more successfully to promote the learning and accomplishment of the student. They may develop shared objectives, regular practices, and a united message about the value of education. Cultural similarity between parents and teachers can facilitate better communication. Shared cultural references, languages, and values can help bridge any communication gaps that may exist. This improved communication enables parents and teachers to collaborate more effectively, exchange valuable insights about the student's progress, and address any challenges or concerns promptly.

Moreover, it is evident that there is in fact a significant relationship changes in family and school settings and attainment of learning outcomes. (.368**) It is crucial to remember that while home and school environment have a big impact on learning outcomes, they don't work alone. Both environments interact and have an impact on one another, resulting in a complicated web of variables that can affect a student's educational success. Positive learning outcomes for pupils may be increased by collaboration between families and schools, such as through excellent communication and partnership.

On the other hand, the table infers that there is no correlation between changes in family and school setting and academic achievement (.230) and persistence (.249). It suggests that factors such as changes in family structure, home environment, or school settings do not significantly impact students' academic performance. Other factors such as individual motivation, teacher quality, or innate abilities may have a greater influence on academic achievement. It highlights the importance of recognizing individual differences among students. While some students may be more resilient and able to adapt to changes in family or school settings without significant impact on their academic performance, others may require additional support or interventions to overcome such changes. Also, it suggests that students' persistence is not significantly influenced by changes in family or school settings. Instead,

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

factors such as personal motivation, self-discipline, and internal drive may have a stronger impact on their persistence in academic pursuits.

In addition, it can be seen that there is indeed a significant relationship between academic achievement and view of scope and function (.368**). Parents' and instructors' viewpoints and convictions may have a significant influence on a student's academic achievement and overall educational experience. It is important to remember that while the opinions of parents and teachers can have a big impact on academic performance, other factors like student motivation, unique talents, and external factors (like socioeconomic status, access to resources) also have a big impact on how well students perform in school.

However, there is no relationship found between view and scope and functions of parents and teachers and persistence (.263) which means earning for family, fulfilling responsibilities of parents has nothing to do with student's attendance in class, coping capabilities of students and student's eagerness to finish his/her task. In this result, we can infer that there are some students who are not acknowledging their parent's sacrifices. Usually, those students who are deprived of quality time from parents who works seven days a week. Also, the table 16 also shows that there is no correlation found between view of scope and function and attainment of learning outcomes (.138). The result in the table implies that the ability to earn for a family and fulfill parental responsibilities is not directly connected to a child's performance in exams or the sharing of their knowledge in the classroom. The implication here is that a parent's capacity to provide for their family and fulfill their parental duties is not solely dependent on their child's academic achievements or their active participation in sharing knowledge in the classroom. The statement suggests that other factors, such as the parent's own skills, qualifications, job opportunities, financial circumstances, and personal attributes, play a more significant role in their ability to support their family. Additionally, the result implies that a child's academic performance and classroom participation may not have a direct impact on their parents' ability to earn a living or fulfill their parental responsibilities. These responsibilities typically extend beyond a child's educational pursuits and are influenced by various factors within the family and societal context.

As such, based from the findings presented in Table 16, with regards to the significant relationship between parent-teacher ecology to the academic performance of learners, it can be seen that there is indeed a significant relationship mostly between the children's participation in learning activities and persistence (.385**), attainment of learning outcomes (.393**), changes in family and school settings (.368**) and view of scope and function (.368**) and thus indicating a significant relationship in these aspects for academic performance and parent-teacher ecology and partially sustaining the null hypothesis of no significant relationship found.

Table 17. Significant Relationship between the Parent-Teacher Ecology to the Social Behavior of Learners

Parent-Teacher Ecology	Social Behavior			
	Peer Relation	Self-Management	Academic Behavior	Social Competence
Similarity of culture and values;	.449**	.453**	.463**	.516**
Changes in family and school settings;	.234	.312*	.351*	.295*
View of scope and function	.368**	.264	.006	.216

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The table 17 displays the significant relationship between parent-teacher ecology and social behavior of learners.

The given data presents the correlation between parent-teacher ecology in terms of similarity of culture and values, changes in family and school settings and view of scope and social behavior in terms of peer relation, self-management, academic behavior and social competence.

Based from the findings presented in Table 17, with regards to the significant relationship between parent-teacher ecology to the social behavior of learners, it can be seen that there is indeed a significant relationship mostly between similarity of cultures and values and peer relation (.449**), self-management (.453**), academic behavior (.463**), social competence (.516**) and view of scope and function (.368**) and thus indicating a significant relationship in these aspects for social behavior and parent-teacher ecology and rejecting the null hypothesis of no significant relationship found. This imply that similarity of culture and values significantly relates to social behavior as a whole. Thus, infers that positive and behavior of parents and teachers towards students' studies, showing good moral values and connecting it to every day's lesson can be reflected to students' cooperation and interaction with others or peers, student's decision making, completing of school's task and activity and even in offering help to others whenever needed. The similarity of culture and values between parents and teachers can have a significant impact on a student's social behavior. When parents and teachers share similar cultural backgrounds and values, it creates a cohesive and supportive environment for the child, which can positively influence their social interactions. It's important to note that even when parents and teachers have different cultural backgrounds and values, effective communication and collaboration can still lead to positive social outcomes for students. Building strong relationships and maintaining open lines of communication between parents and teachers is crucial to supporting a child's social behavior, regardless of cultural similarities or differences.

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

Also, there is significant relationship between changes in family and school settings and self-management (.312*) and academic behavior (.351*) which means that improved interactions with one another in family and school, daily communication, and involvement of parents in different events in school and home has something to do with student's adjustment to different behavioral expectations across settings, respecting other people and helping others. To add, there is indeed significant relationship between changes in family and school setting and student's social competence (.295*). Which signify that improved interactions with one another in family and school, daily communication, and involvement of parents in different events has positive correlation to student's participation in group discussion and activities.

On the other hand, view of scope and functions have no significant relationship as to self-management (.264), academic behavior (.006) and social competence (.215) which indicates that parents earning to support the family, fulfilling their responsibility and parent's attending school events has nothing to do with student's completion of school activities, appropriate response to teachers, offering help to others and student's adjustment to expectations. Even though parents' earning to support the family and fulfilling their responsibilities, as well as their attendance at school events, may not directly impact a student's completion of school activities, these factors can still have an indirect influence on a student's educational outcomes. When parents work to support the family, it can contribute to the overall stability and well-being of the household. Financial security and a stable home environment can create a conducive atmosphere for learning, reduce stressors, and provide resources necessary for a student's educational success. Additionally, parents' fulfillment of their responsibilities, such as providing a safe and supportive home environment, meeting basic needs, and ensuring access to education, can create a foundation that supports a student's engagement in school activities. The implication of this result is that there is no significant relationship between the view of scope and functions of parents and three specific areas: self-management, academic behavior, and social competence. This means that factors such as parents' earning to support the family, fulfilling their responsibilities, and attending school events do not have a direct impact on a student's completion of school activities, appropriate response to teachers, offering help to others, and adjustment to expectations. In other words, these specific aspects of a student's behavior and performance in school are not influenced by how parents perceive their role and responsibilities

To sum up, with regards to the significant relationship between parent-teacher ecology to the social behavior of learners, it can be seen that there is indeed a significant relationship mostly between the peer relation (.449**), self-management (.453**), academic behavior (.463**), social competence (.516**) and view of scope and function (.368**) and thus indicating a significant relationship in these aspects for social behavior and parent-teacher ecology and partially sustaining the null hypothesis of no significant relationship found.

The implication of the statement is that the parent-teacher ecology plays a significant role in shaping the social behavior of learners. The findings suggest that there are strong correlations between various aspects of social behavior, such as peer relations, self-management, academic behavior, social competence, and view of scope and function, and the parent-teacher ecology. These correlations indicate that the quality of the parent-teacher relationship, the involvement of parents in the educational process, and the support provided by teachers can have a positive impact on the social behavior of learners.

Furthermore, the statement mentions that these correlations partially support the null hypothesis of no significant relationship found. This implies that while there is evidence of a significant relationship between parent-teacher ecology and certain aspects of social behavior, there may be other factors at play that also influence social behavior and are not captured in the study. Overall, the implication is that fostering a strong parent-teacher partnership and creating a supportive educational environment can contribute to positive social behavior in learners.

LIMITATIONS

The present study was focused on determining and analyzing the perceived effect of home learning environment and parent-teacher ecology towards the academic performance and positive social behavior of Grade 6 pupils in the S.Y. 2022-2023. The target respondents of the study included Grade 6 students currently enrolled in the School Year 2022-2023. As such, the survey questionnaire will be utilized as the main tool for the data gathering process of the research.

Also, this study is limited to student's perception of their academic performance and positive social behavior. This indicates that this study is centered on understanding how students perceived their own achievements in academics and their interactions with others in a positive social context

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the pupil's home learning environment and their perceived academic performance and positive social behavior is partially sustained.

Home Learning Environment and Parent-Teacher Ecology towards Academic Performance and Positive Social Behavior

2. The null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between parent-teacher ecology and student's perceived academic performance and positive social behavior is partially sustained.

Recommendations

This study required the commitment and involvement of the concerned personnel to sustain its effectiveness and reliability, thus, the following recommendations were made.

1. First, in order to strengthen student-respondents' experience in home learning environment, the cooperation and engagement of parents in fulfilling their active role in providing an effective and conducive learning environment is needed to be ensured. Thus, it is recommended to conduct frequent parent-teacher conferences and meetings in order to help the parents to develop better attitude and approaches to guide their children in doing assignments or projects and overall provide them with a conducive learning environment suited for the learning of the students.
2. On the other hand, as for improving academic performance of pupils, classroom activities and situational activities are recommended in order to help the students to develop attitude and approaches to help them to think clearly and make sound decisions in their learning.
3. Group-based classroom activities are also recommended to encourage the students to better cooperate and interact with their classmates and other students and help them to continuously develop their positive social behavior as part of their holistic learning and development.
4. Finally, it is recommended to conduct future studies that will measure academic performance using appropriate assessment since this study focuses on students' perception only.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author would like to express her sincerest gratitude to the Laguna State Polytechnic University – Research and Development Office for the support. Likewise, the same appreciation is extended to all Padre Garcia Central School Students, Teachers and Staff.

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